

Horizon 2020

A technical report on the development of the system

Deliverable number: D3.5

Version 1.0

Project Acronym: HECAT
Project Full Title: Disruptive Technologies Supporting Labour Market Decision Making
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2018-2019-2020
Grant Number: 870702
Project URL: <https://hecat.eu>

Deliverable nature:	Public (PU)
Dissemination level:	REP
Contractual Delivery Date:	M42
Actual Delivery Date	M42
Authors:	assoc. prof. dr. Pavle Boškosi, Jožef Stefan Institute prof. dr. Biljana Mileva Boshkoska, Jožef Stefan Institute

Abstract

This report presents a comprehensive overview of the development process behind a robust and scalable RESTful Application Programming Interface (API) for the MyLabourMarket platform. The report delves into the architectural decisions and design principles that guided the development process. It covers the selection of appropriate technologies, frameworks, and libraries, along with an explanation of the chosen RESTful design patterns. The architectural choices prioritise modularity, scalability, and maintainability to accommodate future system expansions and ensure long-term stability.

The development methodology employed throughout the project is then discussed, emphasizing the agile approach and iterative development cycles. The report elucidates the collaborative nature of the development process, with cross-functional teams comprising working together to ensure high-quality deliverables.

To facilitate an in-depth understanding of the API implementation, the report presents an overview of the core features and functionality offered by the MyLabourMarket platform APIs. The report further outlines the technical challenges encountered during the development process and the corresponding solutions. It explores strategies employed to optimize API performance, enhance security measures, handle large volumes of data, and ensure fault tolerance.

In conclusion, this technical report offers a comprehensive overview of the development journey undertaken to create a robust and scalable RESTful API for the MyLabourMarket platform. It highlights the architectural decisions, design principles, implementation details, and performance evaluations that have contributed to the successful delivery of a high-quality API. The report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, developers, and future researchers interested in understanding the intricacies of building similar systems.

Contents

1	Introduction to HECAT MLM system	1
2	System components	3
2.1	F03 - Job Progression Route	3
2.2	F06 Bespoke Vacancies	3
2.3	Real-time processing	4
2.4	Gathering of data	4
3	Processing of data sources	5
3.1	Slovenian national statistical office data	5
3.2	Eurostat data	5
3.3	Data refresh frequency	5
3.4	Data Processing and Harmonization	5
4	Implementation of AI components	7
4.1	Training and execution of the model	7
4.2	Explainable AI PEX	8
5	Implementation in production environment	9
6	Conclusion	10

List of Figures

1.1	Logical structure of the implemented platform as proposed by at the beginning of the project. .	2
1.2	Structure of the REpresentational State Transfer (REST) API server.	2
2.1	Process of gathering job postings from the web	4
3.1	Data processing flow	6

List of Acronyms

PES	Public Employment Service
API	Application Programming Interface
PEX	Probability of Exit
SORS	Statistical Office of Republic of Slovenia
REST	REpresentational State Transfer

1 Introduction to HECAT MLM system

An API is a set of routines, protocols, and tools for building software applications. APIs allow two pieces of software to talk to each other, even if they are written in different programming languages.

In the context of web services, an API is a way for two web applications to communicate with each other. For example, a weather app might use an API provided by a weather service to get the latest weather forecast. APIs are an essential part of web services. They allow web applications to interact with each other and to access data and services from other websites.

There are many different types of APIs, but they all share some common features. An API typically defines a set of methods that can be called by other applications. Each method has a specific name and takes a specific set of parameters. When an application calls a method, the API returns a response.

The My Labour Market Platform is a website tool developed by the HECAT project. It brings together public data into three themed sections, which allow users (citizens, public sector staff) to manipulate the data and derive meaningful data from the labour market.

The API of the MyLabourMarket platform are grouped into 4 main functional groups:

F03 Decision support tools including: Probability of Exit (PEX), career path tool and social capital tool

F04 Broad statistical features

F06 Job quality estimation and

General features that contain the most typical and generally publicly available data.

Detailed description of the functionality blocks F0s is given in the deliverable D4.1 [1].

The API is self-documented using OpenAPI structure. The corresponding `yaml` file is available at <http://pinta.ijs.si/hecat/openapi> and the upgraded version is available at <http://pinta.ijs.si/hecat/api/v2/openapi>.

The diagram in Figure 1.1 illustrates a process flow in the system.

1. **User request JSON:** The process starts with a user requesting JSON data.
2. **Memcache:** The system checks the Memcache, which is a high-performance in-memory caching system. It serves as a temporary storage for frequently accessed data.
3. **Present Path:** If the response is present in the Memcache the requested JSON data is available in the Memcache and is directly provided to the user.
4. **Not Present Path:** If the response is not present in the Memcache, the system takes the path indicated by the arrow labeled "Not Present." This indicates that the requested JSON data needs to be generated.
5. **Execute Python AI model:** In this step, the system executes a Python AI model to generate the required JSON data.
6. **Generate JSON:** The system generates the JSON data based on the execution of the Python AI model.
7. **Send JSON back to the user:** Finally, the system sends the generated JSON data back to the user.

In summary, the diagram represents a process flow where the system checks if the requested JSON data is available in the Memcache. If it is present, the system directly sends it back to the user. If not, the system executes a Python AI model to generate the JSON data and sends it back to the user. This flow optimizes the response time by utilizing caching and dynamically generating data when necessary.

The system is built using various technologies to accomplish its functionalities. The core framework for developing the system is Django, a high-level Python web framework that provides a robust foundation for building web applications. Django offers a wide range of features and tools that enable efficient development, including

Figure 1.1: Logical structure of the implemented platform as proposed by at the beginning of the project.

a powerful ORM (Object-Relational Mapping) for database interactions, a secure authentication system, and a flexible URL routing mechanism.

The AI models utilized in the system are built using Torch, a popular open-source machine learning library. Torch provides a rich ecosystem of tools and algorithms for developing and training deep learning models. In addition to Torch, the AI models also incorporate the principles of Variational Bayes [2], a statistical inference technique that enables modeling uncertainty in machine learning tasks. By leveraging Torch and Variational Bayes, the system can harness the power of advanced AI algorithms and make predictions based on complex data patterns.

The decision models employed in the system are built using DEX, a decision modeling language and framework. DEX allows for the creation and deployment of decision models that aid in making informed choices based on various criteria and objectives. By using DEX, the system can incorporate sophisticated decision-making logic into its processes, enhancing its ability to make optimal decisions in dynamic and complex scenarios.

By combining Django for the web framework, Torch and Variational Bayes for AI models, and DEX for decision modeling, the system achieves a robust and comprehensive solution that leverages the strengths of each technology. The schematic representation is shown in Figure 1.2. This integration enables efficient web development, advanced AI capabilities, and intelligent decision-making, providing a powerful platform for addressing the needs of users and delivering valuable outcomes.

Figure 1.2: Structure of the REST API server.

2 System components

The components F03 and F06 of the system are built using the DEX Python implementation from the Dexpy repository [3]. DEX is a decision modeling language and framework that allows for the creation and deployment of decision models. By utilizing the DEX Python implementation, the system benefits from the powerful capabilities of DEX in modeling and optimizing decision processes.

The decision model in the system can be provided in either an XML file format or as a set of pandas tables. Pandas is a popular open-source data manipulation and analysis library for Python, providing high-performance, easy-to-use data structures and data analysis tools. With pandas, the system can efficiently handle and process the decision model represented as structured data, facilitating seamless integration with the DEX Python implementation.

More information about DEX and its Python implementation can be found at DEXpy repository [3] and in [4].

2.1 F03 - Job Progression Route

The F03 module in the system is responsible for analyzing and predicting job progression routes for job seekers. The input structures for this module can be dynamically generated from REST endpoints, allowing for flexible and real-time retrieval of relevant data. By integrating with external systems through REST APIs, the module can fetch up-to-date information such as job histories, educational qualifications, and skills of job seekers. These dynamically generated input structures serve as the foundation for analyzing job progression possibilities.

The evaluation of the F03 module is conducted using Slovenian Public Employment Service (PES) data. PES data provides valuable insights into the employment dynamics, including job transitions and career paths of individuals. By leveraging this data source¹, the module can make informed predictions and recommendations regarding job progression routes for job seekers. The evaluation process is designed to handle large-scale data efficiently, utilizing a multi-processing platform to ensure timely execution. Additionally, to optimize performance and response time, the inputs and corresponding responses are cached in the Memcache, enabling quick retrieval of previously processed data.

2.2 F06 Bespoke Vacancies

The F06 module in the system focuses on generating bespoke vacancies tailored to the unique needs and qualifications of job seekers. Similar to the F03 module, the input structures for F06 can also be dynamically generated from REST endpoints. This flexibility allows the module to integrate with external systems and retrieve relevant information about job seekers, including their skills, preferences, and location.

The evaluation process for the F06 module relies on two primary data sources: the EWSS (European Work Satisfactory Survey) and job postings. The procedure and the underlying data structures are described in deliverables D3.2 [5] and D2.2 [6]. Combined with real-time job postings data, the module can identify emerging trends, specific job requirements, and industry demands. By leveraging this data, the F06 module can generate bespoke vacancies that align with the current job market landscape.

¹It should be noted that the data source used for this module is proprietary and details can not be shared due to privacy issues. It is described in deliverable D3.2 [5].

2.3 Real-time processing

To ensure efficient execution and timely results, the evaluation process of the both modules utilizes a multi-processing platform. This allows for parallel processing of data and speeds up the generation of results. Furthermore, to optimize performance and reduce redundant calculations, both input data and corresponding responses are cached in the Memcache, enabling quick access to previously processed information.

By dynamically generating input structures from REST endpoints and utilizing relevant data sources for evaluation, both the F03 and F06 modules of the system offer personalized and up-to-date insights for job seekers, enabling informed decision-making and improved job matching outcomes.

2.4 Gathering of data

To gather job postings, the system follows a comprehensive process that involves scraping web data, analyzing text using ESCO and NLP methods, utilizing OSM inverse geocoding, and storing the results in a MongoDB database. Each component is built as a container image, ensuring portability and easy deployment.

Scraping Web Data: The system periodically scrapes job postings from various websites to collect up-to-date information. Web scraping involves extracting data from HTML web pages, automating the process of visiting websites, navigating through pages, and retrieving relevant job posting details. By scraping data periodically, the system ensures it captures the latest job openings available on the web.

ESCO and NLP Analysis: After collecting job postings, the system leverages ESCO (European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations) and NLP (Natural Language Processing) methods to analyze the text content of each job posting. ESCO provides a standardized occupational classification system, and by employing NLP techniques, the system can extract key information, such as required skills, qualifications, and job responsibilities, from the job posting texts. This analysis helps determine the appropriate ISCO (International Standard Classification of Occupations) codes for each job posting, enhancing the accuracy of job matching.

OSM Inverse Geocoding: The system utilizes OSM (OpenStreetMap) inverse geocoding to obtain the GPS coordinates of the job posting addresses. Inverse geocoding involves converting textual addresses into geographical coordinates. By geocoding the job posting addresses, the system gains access to precise location information, enabling geographical analysis and mapping of job opportunities.

Storing in MongoDB: The gathered job posting data, along with the analyzed ESCO and NLP results and geocoded coordinates, is stored in a MongoDB database. MongoDB is a popular NoSQL database that offers flexibility and scalability, making it suitable for handling large volumes of unstructured data. Storing the results in MongoDB facilitates efficient retrieval and querying of job postings for further analysis and job matching purposes.

The components involved in gathering job postings, namely web scraping, ESCO and NLP analysis, OSM inverse geocoding, and MongoDB storage, are built as container images. Containerization allows for encapsulating each component with its dependencies, ensuring consistency and easy deployment across different environments.

Figure 2.1: Process of gathering job postings from the web

3 Processing of data sources

The HECAT project relied predominantly on data sourced from Slovenia. In this report, we will explore the statistical data sources used in the MLM tool, highlighting the significance of the Slovenian national statistical office and Eurostat's Labour Force Survey (LFS) and Survey on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) databases. We will delve into the availability and accessibility of these data sources, the frequency of data refresh, and the data processing techniques employed to ensure consistency across datasets. By leveraging these diverse sources, the project aims to extend its reach EU-wide, providing comprehensive insights into labor market dynamics and living standards.

3.1 Slovenian national statistical office data

The project relies on data provided by the Slovenian national statistical office, which serves as a valuable source of information on various socio-economic indicators within the country. This data encompasses a wide range of topics, including employment, wages, education, and living conditions. The Slovenian national statistical office collects and disseminates data through REST web services, following the common practice of other EU national statistical offices. This allows for easy access and integration of the Slovenian data into the project's analysis.

3.2 Eurostat data

Eurostat's LFS and SILC databases play a crucial role in the project's data acquisition process. The LFS provides comprehensive information on employment, unemployment, and other labor market characteristics across European countries. SILC, on the other hand, offers insights into income distribution, poverty rates, and living conditions. However, access to Eurostat's micro data is restricted, requiring a specialized agreement to utilize the dataset fully. Nonetheless, the project has established a partnership with Eurostat, enabling them to receive updates from the micro data twice per year.

3.3 Data refresh frequency

The frequency of data refresh varies between the different data sources. The Slovenian national statistical office typically refreshes their data on a quarterly or annual basis, depending on the specific indicators. This periodic update ensures that the project is working with the most recent data available at the national level¹. Eurostat's micro data, obtained through the project's partnership, is also updated twice per year. The regular refresh of data allows for accurate and up-to-date analysis of labor market trends and living standards.

3.4 Data Processing and Harmonization

To ensure consistency and comparability across different datasets, the project employs robust data processing techniques. Specifically, the Eurostat micro data are processed in a manner that enables the extraction of the same statistical constructs available in the Slovenian data. By harmonizing the data processing methods, the project can extend its reach EU-wide. This approach facilitates the identification of common trends, patterns,

¹Should MLM be rolled out to all EU countries, this variable will most likely change.

and challenges across countries, providing a comprehensive understanding of labor market dynamics and living standards within the European Union.

By leveraging both the Statistical Office of Republic of Slovenia (SORS) data and Eurostat's LFS and SILC databases, the project successfully extends its reach EU-wide. The combination of national-level data and broader European data sources allows for a comprehensive analysis of labor market dynamics and living standards. This approach enables the identification of similarities and differences across countries, providing valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders involved in shaping labor market policies and social welfare initiatives.

Figure 3.1: Data processing flow

4 Implementation of AI components

The proposed model introduces a deep artificial neural network (ANN) as a non-linear hazard function. The ANN is capable of efficiently analyzing high-cardinality categorical features through embedding techniques. By leveraging the power of neural networks, the model captures complex relationships and patterns in the data, enabling accurate predictions of employment probabilities over time for individual job seekers.

To estimate the posterior distribution of the ANN parameters, the paper employs a variational Bayes method [2]. This approach allows for probabilistic inference and provides a measure of uncertainty in the model predictions. By incorporating variational Bayes, the model obtains more robust and reliable estimates of the parameters, enhancing the accuracy of the unemployment duration predictions.

The performance of the proposed model is evaluated using a time-to-employment dataset spanning from 2011 to 2020, provided by the Slovenian public employment service. The model's effectiveness is demonstrated in determining the employment probabilities over time for each individual in the dataset. The results showcase the potential of the model in handling multi-dimensional, high-cardinality categorical data, particularly in scenarios where records are censored. The applicability of similar modeling approaches is discussed, highlighting their relevance in various domains, including personal records such as medical records.

The implementation of the model is built upon PyTorch, a popular open-source machine learning framework, which provides a flexible and efficient platform for deep learning tasks. Additionally, the model utilizes Pyro-ppl, a probabilistic programming library built on PyTorch, which enables Bayesian inference and facilitates the estimation of the posterior distribution of the ANN parameters. Pyro-ppl allows for flexible modeling of complex probabilistic systems, making it a suitable tool for the variational Bayes estimation in the proposed model.

Deploying PyTorch models through a Python web API REST allows for seamless integration of machine learning models into production systems. Within the API implementation, the PyTorch model is loaded and initialized, as a pre-trained model. Once the model is loaded, incoming requests containing data to be processed can be sent to the API, which then forwards the data to the model for inference. The model generates predictions or performs desired computations, and the API returns the results back to the client as a response.

When serving PyTorch models through a Python web API REST, it is crucial to ensure scalability, performance, and security. To handle multiple concurrent requests efficiently, the API can be designed to utilize asynchronous processing or distributed computing techniques. Overall, serving PyTorch models through a Python web API REST offers a flexible and scalable solution to deploy machine learning models, enabling easy integration into diverse applications and systems.

4.1 Training and execution of the model

The Pyro survival model, utilized in this study, is trained offline using the HPC-River infrastructure, leveraging its high-performance computing capabilities. The HPC-River infrastructure provides the necessary computational resources to efficiently train the model on a large-scale dataset, which is sourced from the Slovenian public employment service. This dataset encompasses a significant temporal range, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of unemployment dynamics. By training the model offline, researchers can optimize the model's architecture, hyperparameters, and training process to ensure accurate and robust predictions of job seeker outcomes.

The execution of the Pyro survival model exhibits remarkable computational efficiency and scalability, thanks to the HPC-River infrastructure. The utilization of high-performance computing resources enables the model

to process large volumes of data and perform complex computations in a time-efficient manner. This scalability ensures that the model can handle increasing dataset sizes and accommodate future growth and updates. Moreover, the computational efficiency of the model allows for timely execution, providing rapid insights into the probability of job seekers finding employment as a function of time. This combination of computational efficiency and scalability enables researchers to obtain accurate and reliable results while efficiently utilizing the available computing resources.

4.2 Explainable AI PEX

The above-mentioned survival model, although effective in estimating time-to-employment, is considered non-explainable. Explainable AI refers to the capability of an AI model or system to provide transparent and interpretable explanations for its predictions or decisions. It allows users to understand the underlying factors and reasoning behind the model's output. There are a number of techniques that can be used to achieve explainable AI. Some of the most common techniques include:

Feature importance This technique identifies the features that are most important for a model's predictions.

This can be done by looking at the coefficients of a linear model or by using a technique like SHAP.

Local explanations These explanations focus on the specific input data that was used to make a prediction.

This can be done by using a technique like LIME or by visualizing the decision boundaries of a model.

Counterfactual explanations These explanations show how a model's prediction would change if the input data were changed. This can be done by using a technique like Counterfactual Regret Minimization or by generating adversarial examples.

The choice of technique will depend on the specific model and the type of explanation that is desired. For example, if a user wants to understand the overall factors that influence a model's predictions, then feature importance may be a good choice. If a user wants to understand how a model's predictions would change if the input data were changed, then counterfactual explanations may be a better choice.

In the case of the mentioned survival model, it lacks the ability to provide intuitive explanations for its predictions, making it challenging to comprehend how specific features or variables influence the time-to-employment estimations.

To address this limitation, an alternative version of the survival model has been developed based on oblique predictive clustering trees. Oblique predictive trees are a machine learning technique capable of handling both categorical and continuous data, and they can model complex non-linear relationships between variables. Unlike traditional survival analysis methods, this approach treats censored data as missing data, which opens up the possibility of performing survival analysis using structured output prediction in a semi-supervised multi-target regression setting.

The second implementation focuses on applying the semi-supervised oblique predictive clustering tree method to estimate time-to-employment using a real dataset obtained from the Public Employment Services in Slovenia. This dataset consists of time-to-employment records along with personal and professional characteristics of job seekers. The performance of the proposed approach is compared with six other state-of-the-art AI methods to assess its effectiveness.

It is worth noting that this implementation represents a **novel application** of semi-supervised oblique predictive clustering trees for survival analysis. By utilizing this approach, the model aims to enhance the interpretability of the predictions and provide valuable insights into the factors influencing the time-to-employment for job seekers.

5 Implementation in production environment

The implementation of the job postings analysis system in a production environment comprises several key components. The system leverages different technologies to handle specific functionalities efficiently. These components include:

Tomcat Web server for ESCO API: The ESCO API is served using the Tomcat Web server. Tomcat provides a robust and scalable platform for hosting the ESCO API, which is essential for retrieving information about job classifications and skills. By utilizing Tomcat, the system ensures reliable access to ESCO data, enabling accurate analysis and categorization of job postings.

Nominatim Web server for OSM inverse geocoding: The Nominatim Web server is employed for OSM (Open-StreetMap) inverse geocoding. Geocoding is the process of converting addresses into geographic coordinates. In this case, OSM inverse geocoding allows the system to obtain GPS coordinates corresponding to job posting addresses. Nominatim, as a geocoding solution, ensures accurate and efficient retrieval of geographical information, enabling precise analysis and visualization of job postings' spatial distribution.

Django/Apache for the main API: The main API, responsible for handling job seeker-related functionalities and serving the core features of the system, is implemented using Django framework with Apache as the web server. Django offers a high-level, versatile toolkit for building web applications, allowing for efficient development and maintenance of the main API. Apache serves as a reliable and widely-used web server, ensuring smooth handling of incoming requests and facilitating seamless integration with Django.

MongoDB for job postings analysis: Job postings analysis is performed using MongoDB, a NoSQL database designed for handling large volumes of unstructured data. MongoDB provides the flexibility and scalability required to store and analyze diverse job postings data. By leveraging MongoDB, the system can efficiently process and query job postings, enabling various analytical tasks such as trend analysis, keyword extraction, and clustering.

SQLite for broad statistical concepts from the national statistical office: Broad statistical concepts obtained from the national statistical office are stored and managed using SQLite, a lightweight relational database management system. SQLite offers simplicity and ease of use, making it suitable for handling smaller datasets and performing essential statistical operations. By utilizing SQLite, the system can store and retrieve statistical concepts efficiently, supporting various calculations, aggregations, and comparisons.

Each of the aforementioned servers and components is encapsulated within its own container image, utilizing Docker technology. Docker provides a containerization platform that allows for packaging applications and their dependencies into isolated, lightweight containers. Containerization ensures portability, reproducibility, and consistency across different environments, making it easier to deploy and scale the system.

Moreover, the implementation can be expanded on a large scale using orchestration tools such as Kubernetes. Kubernetes is an open-source container orchestration platform that automates the deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications. By utilizing Kubernetes, the system can efficiently manage a cluster of containers, distribute workload, ensure high availability, and dynamically scale resources based on demand. This enhances the system's scalability, fault tolerance, and resilience, enabling seamless operation in a production environment with a potentially large user base.

In summary, the implementation of the job postings analysis system in a production environment involves utilizing Tomcat, Nominatim, Django with Apache, MongoDB, and SQLite. Each component is encapsulated within its own container image using Docker. This containerization approach ensures portability and ease of deployment. The system can be further expanded on a large scale using orchestration tools like Kubernetes, enabling efficient management and scalability.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the implementation described above presents a comprehensive and open-source solution for job seekers' data analysis and prediction. The complete system, which encompasses various components and technologies, offers a powerful platform for understanding and modeling unemployment dynamics.

The entire implementation, including the core functionality and supporting systems, is made available as an open-source project. The code repository, located at https://repo.ijs.si/pboskoski/hecat_django, provides access to the source code, documentation, and resources required to deploy and utilize the system. By making the implementation open source, it promotes collaboration, transparency, and community-driven enhancements, allowing researchers, developers, and organizations to benefit from the collective knowledge and expertise of the community.

It is worth highlighting that all the libraries and supporting systems utilized within the implementation are also open-source. This emphasizes the commitment to open standards, fostering interoperability, and enabling extensibility. The use of open-source libraries ensures that the system remains flexible, customizable, and adaptable to different use cases and evolving requirements.

The availability of the complete implementation as open source, along with the open-source nature of the used libraries and supporting systems, encourages innovation, encourages reproducibility, and facilitates the exchange of ideas and best practices within the research and development community. This approach empowers individuals and organizations to leverage the system's capabilities, contribute to its improvement, and adapt it to their specific needs.

In conclusion, the open-source implementation described today provides a robust and accessible platform for job seekers' data analysis. It allows users to explore unemployment dynamics, estimate time-to-employment, and gain valuable insights into labor market trends. The openness of the implementation, coupled with the use of open-source libraries and supporting systems, ensures transparency, collaboration, and continuous improvement, making it a valuable resource for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike.

Bibliography

- [1] Interaction design framework. Technical Report D4.1, Technalia, 2021.
- [2] Pavle Boškosi, Matija Perne, Martina Rameša, and Biljana Mileva Boshkoska. Variational bayes survival analysis for unemployment modelling. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 229:107335, 2021. ISSN 0950-7051. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2021.107335>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950705121005979>.
- [3] Biljana Mileva Boshkoska. Dexpy, 2023. URL <https://repo.ijs.si/bmileva/dexpy>.
- [4] Wes McKinney. Data structures for statistical computing in python. In *Python in Science Conference*, 2010. doi: 10.25080/majora-92bf1922-00a.
- [5] A training set of anonymised data that can be used for development and evaluation of algorithms. Technical Report D3.2, Jožef Stefan Institute, 2021.
- [6] Ayo Næsborg-Andersen, Snorre Frid-Nielsen, Janine Leschke, and Clément Brébion. Technical report data sources and data protection for algorithm development. Technical Report D2.2, 2021. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7914776>.